

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	2010	B		Min: 63.0804 Max: 63.1387	1297 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropic

In cross-section? Yes No
 In elevation drawing? Yes No
 Photos: Yes No #: 1322-132
 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: Fill of semi-circular pit in Room I
 Covered by: SU: 1232
 Fills: SU: 1298
 Filled by: SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction
 FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX				
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay 15% silt 80% sand 5% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft </td> <td> <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Compaction	Color	<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Depth: Original Not Original

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1232	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 1298

OBSERVATIONS

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: W wall of Room I
 Shape: semi-circular

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): Nope
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): no inclusions
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commigled other (specify)

<p>For cuts complete this section:</p> <p>Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded Observations:</p>	<p>Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):</p>
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For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

fill within a semicircular foundation in floor
SV1231

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	CAK	on	28-07-2010
Revised by	CHH	on	28-07-2010
PDFd by		on	
Entered by		on	